

MINI VIDAS[®]

Simply reliable

PIONEERING DIAGNOSTICS

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With **MINI VIDAS®** your lab can carry out tests simply and quickly, in a self-contained, space-saving unit. Its user-friendly Load & Go concept means your teams can process up to 36 tests an hour. It also offers excellent reliability, with a MTBF (1) of over 1,100 days.

An improved Design for Increased User Comfort

DESIGN

- Streamline your workflow by optimizing test loading
- Increase user-friendliness for data entry and reporting patient results
- Compact solution with integrated computer & printer

RELIABLE

- System robustness (MTBF⁽¹⁾ > 1,100 days)
- Single dose concept, ready-to-use reagents
- Automated barcode identification
- Just Load & Go

FLEXIBLE

- Two independent 6-test sections
- Processing of different parameters simultaneously
- Packaging suite to different test volumes (30 or 60 tests)
- 100 parameters available⁽²⁾

	MINI VIDAS®
Weight	40 kg (88 lbs)
Voltage	100-240 VAC
Electric Consumption	1.5-0.8 A
Frequency	50-60 Hz
Power	150 Watts

* SPR: Solid Phase Receptacle
 (1) MTBF = Mean Time Between Failure
 (2) Pending list of assay registered in a specific country

Discover the VIDAS community and become a member by registering on www.myvidas.com

